

Amino Derivatives of Tungsten (VI) Chloride. Part II*

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The amino derivatives of tungsten (VI) chloride have been prepared by the action of the metal chloride on several secondary and tertiary amines, and heterocyclic bases; their properties have been studied and structures discussed.

Ekeley (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **31**, 664) observed that freshly prepared tungstic acid dissolved readily in aqueous solutions of most aliphatic amines with the formation of substituted ammonium tungstates. Lindner and Kohlar (*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1924, **140**, 357) prepared a number of complex salts with pyridine. Jonassen *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 271) found that when $K_3W_2Cl_9$ was refluxed under anhydrous anaerobic conditions in pyridine or aniline, three chloride ions were displaced with the formation of non-electrolytes: $W_2Cl_6(C_5H_5N)_3$ or $W_2Cl_6(C_6H_5NH_2)_3$.

Preparation and properties of the compounds formed by the action of tungsten (VI) chloride on some aromatic primary mono- and diamines have already been studied (this *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 588). The work has now been extended to study the action of tungsten(VI) chloride on some secondary and tertiary amines, and heterocyclic bases.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amines and heterocyclic bases used were of Merck's or B.D.H. 'extra pure' quality. WCl_6 was prepared as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*). Ether was distilled over metallic sodium; AnalaR CCl_4 was dried over and distilled from P_2O_5 immediately before use.

A dilute solution of the amine in CCl_4 was added to tungsten (VI) chloride in CCl_4 with constant shaking till the precipitation was complete and the amine was in slight excess. The precipitate was filtered and washed with dry CCl_4 till free of amine, all the operations having been carried out in nitrogen atmosphere. It was dried in vacuum.

In the case of tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases, an ethereal solution of these was added to tungsten (VI) chloride in CCl_4 and the precipitate was washed with ether till free of the reactants. The compounds obtained being hygroscopic were quickly transferred to a vacuum desiccator and dried for 2 to 3 days.

Tungsten, chlorine and nitrogen were estimated as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

General Properties.—All the compounds are coloured, insoluble in CCl_4 , ether, and benzene, but sparingly soluble in ethanol. The compounds formed with tertiary amines are, however, sparingly soluble in CCl_4 . These are fairly stable in dry atmosphere, but when exposed to moist air they absorb moisture and decompose. The products do not give a sharp melting point and decompose when heated. When these are heated with sodalime, the corresponding amine or heterocyclic base separates out and condenses in the cooler parts of the tube.

* Part I: This *Journal*, 1960, **37**, 588.

TABLE I

Amine or heterocyclic base.	Product.	Colour.	% Tungsten.		% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Methylamine	$W(C_2H_5NH_2)_6Cl_6$	Ash	17.62	17.71	20.10	20.47	8.118	8.089
2. Ethylamine	$W(C_2H_5NH.C_2H_5)_6Cl_6$	Dark brown	16.12	16.56	18.87	19.15	7.493	7.565
3. Benzylamine	$W(C_6H_5NH.CH_2.C_6H_5)_6Cl_6$	Dirty brown	24.39	24.12	27.39	27.89	3.654	3.672
4. Diphenylamine	$W(C_6H_5NH.C_6H_5)_6Cl_6$	Brown	24.78	25.03	28.96	28.95	3.790	3.812
5. Diphenylbenzidine	$W(C_6H_5.NH.C_6H_5)_6Cl_6$	Yellowish green	13.16	13.10	15.09	15.15	5.931	5.982
6. Dimethylaniline	$W[C_6H_4N(CH_3)_2]_6Cl_6$	Blue	28.63	28.80	33.04	33.31	4.423	4.385
7. Diethylaniline	$W[C_6H_4N(C_2H_5)_2]_6Cl_6$	Bluish green	26.29	26.48	30.40	30.61	4.071	4.032
8. Dibenzylaniline	$W[Ph.N(CH_2Ph)_2]_6Cl_6$	Grey	19.60	19.51	22.12	22.56	3.104	2.970
9. Benzylideneaniline	$W(Ph.CH=NPh)_6Cl_6$	"	24.16	24.24	27.87	28.03	3.719	3.692
10. <i>p</i> -Aminodimethylaniline	$W(Me_2N.C_6H_4NH_2)_6Cl_6$	Violet	23.01	22.86	26.32	26.43	10.160	10.440
11. <i>p</i> -Aminodiethylaniline	$W(Et_2N.C_6H_4NH_2)_6Cl_6$	Black	20.23	20.69	23.91	23.93	9.506	9.454
12. Dimethyl- <i>p</i> -toluidine	$W[CH_3.C_6H_4N(CH_3)_2]_6Cl_6$	Bluish grey	27.59	27.58	31.81	31.90	4.129	4.201
13. Diethyl- <i>p</i> -toluidine	$W[CH_3.C_6H_4N(C_2H_5)_2]_6Cl_6$	Grey	23.16	23.45	29.16	29.43	3.793	3.876
14. Triethylamine	$W(C_2H_5)_3N]_6Cl_6$	Buff	30.70	30.73	35.08	35.53	4.712	4.678
15. Pyridine	$W(C_5H_5N)_6Cl_6$	Dark brown	33.02	33.16	38.10	38.34	..	..
16. 2-Aminopyridine	$W(NH_2.C_5H_4N)_6Cl_6$	Dark reddish brown liquid	27.28	27.10	31.23	31.34	..	..
17. Piperidine	$W(C_5H_{11}N)_6Cl_6$	Reddish brown	32.16	32.47	37.46	37.53	..	..
18. α -Picoline	$W(C_6H_7N)_6Cl_6$	Yellowish brown	31.36	31.57	36.44	36.51	..	..
19. γ -Picoline	Do	Blue	31.60	31.57	36.17	36.51	..	..
20. Quinoline	$W(C_8H_7N)_6Cl_6$	Brown	27.99	28.10	32.23	32.48	..	..

DISCUSSION

In the case of secondary amines, the reaction is similar to that with primary amines with the difference that the precipitate appears only on shaking the mixture for a long time at the room temperature, showing thereby the weak co-ordinating power of :NH group. Six molecules of the amine combine with one molecule of WCl_6 except in the case of benzylaniline and diphenylamine, when only two molecules of these combine with one molecule of WCl_6 , which is probably due to steric hindrance.

The compounds formed with tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases are not so stable as those obtained with primary or secondary amines, and in most cases only two molecules of the amine or heterocyclic base combine with one of tungsten (VI) chloride, which is probably due to the weak co-ordinating power of :N group and may be represented as $W(2Am)Cl_6$.

With diphenylbenzidine, *p*-aminodimethylaniline, *p*-aminodiethylaniline, and 2-amino-pyridine compounds, in which the ratio of WCl_6 : amine or heterocyclic base = 1:3, are formed. These compounds are very stable, due probably to formation of chelate compounds.

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